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“LIFE’S NOT A SPRINT”

Take each day like steps on a stairwell
Take it slow, savor the joys and peril.
Other's timeline, deadlines and fine lines,
Not one is alike, so hush with the "What about mine?"

Life's no race, focus on leaving a trace,
What matters is whether you handle it with grace.
Time is tricky, and expectations can get messy.
Enjoy the journey, each day should end like a party.

Breathe through, breathe deep,
Gather the littlest moments, let it seep.
Don't chase, don't compare
God is with you, He'll take you there.